

I.FAST

Innovation Fostering in Accelerator Science and Technology

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DELIVERABLE REPORT

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ABSTRACT

The fundamental goal of the Task 3 of WP3 of IFAST (WP3.3) is to identify how the accelerator science and technology community can improve the effectiveness of industry-research institution collaboration at early stages. In this deliverable report, the workplan of WP3.3 is described, together with the collection of feedback both from industrial partners and research institutions to the central issue addressed. An effort has been made to guarantee a representative contact with the industrial sector. The analysis developed has been discussed in a second iteration with industry and research institutions and their feedback are compiled. The conclusions obtained provide a number of topics to address. None of them are simple, nor implementable at a short-range without a strong commitment of the whole community. Some of them may be controversial, since they can affect to the internal strategy of research institutions and may represent an effort difficult to accomplish without implementing specific plans that will demand funds and resources. In this context, the ideas collected and discussed in this work with the industry and the research institutions may represent a valuable reference for incoming initiatives, both for specific developments and for wider roadmaps of the accelerator science and technology community.

I.FAST Consortium, 2024

For more information on IFAST, its partners and contributors please see <https://ifast-project.eu/>

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	Name	Partner	Date
Authored by	J.M. Perez, E. Fernandez, M. Moreno	CIEMAT INEUSTAR CDTI	01/02/2024
Reviewed by	M. Morandin M. Vretenar [on behalf of Steering Committee]	INFN CERN	15/02/2024 16/02/2024
Approved by	Steering Committee		16/02/2024

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Executive summary

The fundamental goal of the Task 3 of WP3 of IFAST (WP3.3) is to identify how the accelerator science and technology community can improve the effectiveness of industry-research institution collaboration at early stages. In this deliverable report, the workplan of WP3.3 is described, together with the collection of feedback both from industrial partners and research institutions to the central issue addressed in this task.

An effort has been made to guarantee a representative contact with the industrial sector involved on Accelerator Science and Technology. The analysis developed has been discussed in a second iteration with industry and research institutions and their feedback are compiled.

The conclusions obtained provide a number of topics to address. None of them are simple, nor implementable at a short-range without a strong commitment of the whole community.

Some of them may be controversial, since they can affect to the internal strategy of research institutions and may represent an effort difficult to accomplish without implementing specific plans that will demand funds and resources.

In this context, the ideas collected and discussed in this work with the industry and the research institutions may represent a valuable reference for incoming initiatives, both for specific developments and for wider roadmaps of the accelerator science and technology community

1 Introduction

Within the community of Accelerator Science and Technology (ASc&T), a continuous and increasing need for the involvement of industry has been defined as a priority. In previous projects, fluent contacts were set out between research institutions and industry. Similar approaches have been conducted by ILO (Industrial Liaison Offices) associations, research infrastructures (RI) and technological infrastructures (TI), as well as other stakeholders with links to the Science Industry¹.

From the feedback provided by companies participating in previous accelerator projects, it was determined that there exists considerable unexploited potential for industry to positively contribute to R&D activities and/or low TRL research activities, if engaged during the early stages.

The Task 3 of the IFAST work-package 3 (WP3.3) is focused specifically on providing a clear view about the following point: ***how to advance on an early involvement of the industry within the accelerator research and development activities***. For such, the working group has arranged a series of meetings with companies with experience in ASc&T and related fields, has iterated with them on

¹ In this document, the term *Science Industry* is used to define the industry involved in activity related to the design, prototyping, integration, testing and series production of scientific components and instrumentation, either under commercial contracts or within collaboration on research projects.

their responses and compiled their feedback. Other stakeholders were consulted as well, in particular the ILOs of a number of European countries.

This report summarizes the aim and motivation of this work, the methodology used, the interaction with industry, RIs and ILOs, the analysis carried out and, finally, provides some considerations and conclusions on this topic.

2 Analysis of the participation of industry in collaborative R&D activities at early stages

2.1 SPECIFIC AIMS OF WP 3.3

The fundamental goal of WP 3.3 of IFAST is to identify how the accelerator science and technology community can improve the effectiveness of industry-RI collaboration and, in particular, promote the involvement of industry in its activities at the early stages of the proposals (i.e., at low TRL).

From the analysis carried out in projects such as ARIES and AMICI, and via coordinated actions by consortia such as TIARA, it has already been confirmed that an extended involvement of industry in accelerator component development cycles, usually taking place inside the RI and TI facilities, could bring significant benefits that may lead to faster, more robust products and reduction of costs, that can represent a benefit for the companies themselves.

Ideally, this approach would benefit from early common strategies between research labs and industry in order to timely define key aspects such as reliable designs, efficient product evaluation to avoid increasing costs, adequately defining the generation of technical knowledge or fair IP rules, among others topics. But the early engagement of industry on research projects may impose several constraints to the industry partner: higher operational costs, higher risks, decisions and investments pre-market or conflicts of interest, for example.

2.2 BACKGROUND

This work can be considered as a continuation of reviews with wider scope previously done by our community. The material in Section 9 has been used as reference.

Among these reference documents, we highlight the work done within the AMICI project on requirements and conditions for the developing of prototyping in the industry [2].

2.3 INVOLVED ACTORS AND ACTIVITY COVERED

The first layer of actors involved in the work addressed in this document are industries related to accelerator component development, research institutions and ILOs.

The activities covered encompasses mainly the first stages of scientific-technical development, namely: study, design, development, prototyping, integration and tests of components for research purposes. But, on a wider scope, it is also considered industrial development aspects related with the construction of systems, large instruments, facilities, first-of-a-kind industrial equipment and series production of scientific instrumentation.

2.3.1 Industry

At the time of starting this work, there were not a well identified body to interact with the industry target of our study. Except in some specific cases, there are no industry associations that can play this role either, at least in a homogeneous way among the member States (MS) represented in IFAST.

To overcome this limitation, we decided to interact with two different actors related with the Science Industry:

- A representative number of companies via an individual approach. The IFAST project is a suitable framework to make such interactions, since a significant representation of the industries involved on ASc&T are partners or associated partners of the project. Although, as mentioned afterwards, in a second consideration it was decided not to limit this work to the range of IFAST.
- The ILOs themselves, apart from facilitating the contact with the industry, can provide a valuable view to this study. A number of ILOs from different MS have been consulted.

2.3.2 Research institutions and accelerator users

Institutions involved in accelerators, both developers and users, are organized and coordinated via well-known consortia. Apart from the research and technological institutions individually, the most relevant consortia for WP3.3 are:

- For ASc&T institutions, TIARA is a suitable consortium to consult.
- For the specific needs of research and technological infrastructures of accelerators, the AMICI collaboration can provide a wide view. This collaboration is represented on IFAST, in particular in the task 13.1.

2.4 METHODOLOGY IN THIS WORK

The profile of the companies related to ASc&T is not homogeneous. They differ in aspects such as dimension, commercial approaches, proportion of business targeted to scientific applications versus general market or collaboration experience with academia. In most cases, the information they have from our community is partial and selective, limited to the projects and contracts they have specifically participated.

Under these circumstances, in order to gather their opinion on interaction with research institutions at early stages, we thought that it would not be efficient to submit a general questionnaire. Instead, we opted for bi-lateral meetings in order to tailor the interactions to the actual experience and aims of each company. For such, we selected a number of representative industries.

On the other hand, it is important to consider that, in order to keep an adequate level of interest, the number of interactions with industry on issues related to the topics of interest for ASc&T must be optimized.

Similarly, we held bi-lateral meetings with ILOs from a selected number of MS, those considered as the most active in our field.

Finally, we did not limit our contacts to industries involved in IFAST, nor in ASc&T fields. We extended the contacts to industries with experience in other sectors of Big Science, such as space, fusion, astrophysics or medical applications, among others.

2.5 WORK PLAN

The workplan initially designed for WP3.3 was split in 4 steps, namely:

Step 1:

- 1.1. Background. Previous information of interest
- 1.2. Private iteration with related industries. Preliminary feedback.
- 1.3. Inform WP Leaders and Project Leader.

Step 2:

- 2.1. Internal iteration
- 2.2. Definition of key questions
- 2.3. Definition of IFAST companies, and TI, RI, others.

Step 3

- 3.1. Define the contact network (under iterative basis).
- 3.2. B2B meetings with companies in IFAST.
- 3.3. Presence at workshops scheduled in IFAST.

Step 4

- 4.1. Second iteration with selected companies
- 4.2. Iteration with TI, RI
- 4.3. Discussion with representative parties (industry, RI/TI)
- 4.4. Deliverable D3.1. drafting

During the work, due to practical reasons, it was decided to skip point 4.1.

The time line of the work is presented in Table 1.

		2021				2022				2023				2024					
		May	July	Sept	Nov	Jan	March	May	July	Sept	Nov	Jan	March	May	July	Sept	Nov	Jan	March
		Year 1				Year 2				Year 3									
		M0	M2	M4	M8	M10	M12	M14	M16	M18	M20	M22	M24	M26	M28	M30	M32	M34	M36
Step 1	Background. Previous information of interest																		
	Private iteration with related industries. Preliminary feedback.																		
	Inform WP leaders and Project leader for an eventual help																		
Step 2	Internal iteration																		
	Definition of key questions																		
	Definition of IFAST companies, and TI, RI, others																		
Step 3	Define the contact network (under iterative basis)																		
	B2B meetings with companies in IFAST																		
	Workshops programmed in IFAST																		
Step 4	Second iteration with selected companies																		
	Iteration with TI, RI																		
	Discussion with representative parties (Industry, RI/TI)																		
	Deliverable D3.1. drafting																		
	Milestone: M3.3: Collection of feedback from industrial partners and RIs participating in I-FAST. Delivery date: M 15																		
	Deliverable 3.3: Report on extended industrial contributions in R&D activities. Delivery date: month 36																		
		May	July	Sept	Dec	Jan	March	May	July	Sept	Nov	Jan	March	May	July	Sept	Nov	Jan	March
		2021				2022				2023				2024					

Table 1. Timeline of the activities in WP3.3.

3 The key questions

The actual success of a collaboration with industry fundamentally depends on a proper definition of the goals and set out effective working conditions. Other factors significantly affect the outcome, such as the previous information of interests shared or the merging of common interests, among others. In the case of early engagement (collaboration at early stages of the development), these points must be specifically addressed, as well as other issues such as commercial constraints of working far from an established market, more complex funding tools, timing aspects, singular IP issues, etc.

We have compiled a list of points related to the aspects discussed in the paragraph above. This list constituted the basis of our contacts with industry and other stakeholders. The list of questions compiled, so-called *key-questions* in this document, is outlined in Annex I.

These questions evolved through discussion with the companies. Some of them were adapted according to the development of the contacts, for the sake of effectiveness.

It is pointed out that this key-question document was offered to the industries as a guide for our conversation. In some cases, it was revealed to be too exhaustive and broad. In others, we started our talks on the specific points in the list but, during the conversation, we focused on issues based on the experiences of the company and, in frequent cases, the meeting evolved outside the guide proposed.

4 List of contacts

4.1 THE CONTACT WITH THE COMPANIES

Table 2 below shows the list of companies and ILOs contacted, together with the meeting dates scheduled.

We want to highlight that the interaction of ILOs was essential for the success of the industry feedback in the corresponding countries. Without their support, this work would not have been feasible.

It is noteworthy that only two companies refused to reply to our contacts, out of 20.

	Company	Contact	Meeting status	
France	ILO	Nicolas Breton	24/2/22	09:30
	SEF-Technologies	Eric Fanio	9/3/22	09:30
	SODITECH	Adrien Deverre	18/3/22	17:00
Netherlands	ILO	Jan Visser	4/3/22	13:00
	CRYOWORLD	Marcel Keezer	31/3/22	13:00
	HIT	Cock Heemskerck		
Italy	ILO	Mauro Morandin	18/2/22	15:30
	OCEM Power Electronics	Miguel Pretelli	3/3/22	10:10
	CAEN	Ferdinando Giordano	3/3/22	12:00
	ASG	Antonio Pellecchia	22/3/22	14:00
	SAES	Paolo Manini	9/3/22	16:00
	KYMA	Rafaella Geometrante	28/6/21	15:00
Germany	ILO	Friedrich Haug	2/3/22	16:00
	Billfinger Noell	Michael Gehring	1/7/21	13:30
	Trumpf	Marcus Lau	21/4/22	16:00
	Bevatech	Holger Höltermann		
	Research Instruments	Michael Pekeler	21/4/22	14:00
Spain	ILO	Manuel Moreno (*)		
	Spanish Science Industry Association	Erik Fernández (*)		
	AVS	M. Angel Carrera	20/10/21	15:00
	ELYTT	Aitor Echandía	8/10/21	09:00
	BTESA	Juan Lluch	2/6/21	09:15
Sweden	ILO	Fredrik Engelmark	27/4/22	13:30
	Qamcom	Otto Lilja	5/5/22	13:00
	Scandinova Systems	Mikael Lindholm		
	Quantum group			

Denmark	ILO	Jonas Okkels Birk Herik	8/4/22	14:00
	Mark-wedell	Torven Ekvall	21/4/22	10:00

Table 2. List of companies and ILOs contacted. (*) WP3.3 members

4.2 LIST OF INSTITUTIONS CONTACTED

A selection of institutions has been contacted to discuss the feedback obtained from the industries. These were: DESY, CERN and INFN.

The contacts were scheduled in the following dates:

- **CERN:** 07-11-2022 and 28-11-2022;
- **INFN:** 20-12-2022;
- **DESY:** 04-01-2023.

Beside the institutions above, the consortia AMICI and TIARA were informed of the outcome of this analysis via their representatives in CEA, INFN and CIEMAT.

5 Contacts with Industry and Research Institutions

5.1 DISCUSSIONS WITH THE INDUSTRY

A compilation of points addressed and discussed within the iteration with the companies is attached in Annex II.

5.2 DISCUSSION WITH THE RESEARCH/TECHNOLOGICAL INSTITUTIONS

A summary of the compilation provided in Annex II was shared with the institutions and discussed with them in specific meetings. The main outcome of such discussions is presented in Annex III.

In general terms, the institutions agreed that the work done was very complete, being their views very much aligned with most of the messages received from the companies, whilst there remained some difference of opinion in specific points, basically related to:

- the concept of outsourcing technological capability to the industry;
- the feasibility to increase the flexibility in R&D procurements;
- the IP policy suitable for an early collaboration with the industry;
- the viability and interest of directly funding to industries for carrying out pure research activities;
- the viability to merge our technical needs with the ones of other Big Science fields.

5.3 SUMMARY OF THE MAIN TOPICS IDENTIFIED FOR FURTHER ANALYSIS

From the discussions held with companies, ILOs and institutions, it was identified a set of aspects that become a very suitable base for the activities foreseen in the task 4.3 of our Work Plan (see Section 2.5).

We outline below a table of topics compiled from the work done in WP3.3 affecting the early engagement of industry on accelerator R&D activities. It is presented in a SWOT format. The factors below can guide a second discussion with representative parties.

Analysis of factors affecting the early engagement of industry in activities promoted by the AS&T community		
Internal factors	Strengths	Weaknesses
<i>Small potential market size; limited number of suppliers</i>		Labs forced to keep internal know-how and may be interested on limiting the engagement of companies
<i>Labs own significant technical human and material resources. They want to keep the competences of prototyping in house</i>		There is less incentive to engage industry. Academia may become a competitor to industry
<i>R&D service providing</i>	More chances of industry engagement may be originated from the possibility of considering companies not only as suppliers but also as R&D service providers	
<i>Industry owns specific complementary competences</i>	Production aspects can be taken into consideration from the beginning; risk of sub-optimal design (that may imply higher costs at production phase or poor quality of the final products) can be minimized.	
<i>Scientific environment characterized by general openness of the results</i>	May facilitate the transfer of background knowledge from academia to industry	May reduce appeal for companies interested in getting exclusive ownership of the IP produced in the R&D phase

<i>Highly specialized developments, industry personnel may not have sufficient technical knowledge</i>	E&T actions with Labs is an efficient tool to incorporate technical knowledge. R&D activities may attract external resources to support training activities.	Transfer of knowledge to industry may be difficult or too expensive. Training actions attractive for industry should be carried out with a common plan and take place also in industry
<i>Strong interest of some companies in getting exclusive ownership of the IP produced in the R&D phase</i>		May produce a lock-in situation.
<i>IP management</i>	Addressing IP management at early stage meets expectations from industry	May require additional efforts on both sides. IP management not addressed in a proper way: discourage, delays, conflicts.
<i>Limited companies' liability</i>	Engaging the companies at low TRL mitigates their risks	
<i>Lack of clear market perspectives</i>		Companies may not be willing to participate in the R&D activities
<i>R&D early steps developed with no input from the industry sector</i>	May free the developments from too stringent conservative approaches driven by industry	May hinder a synergistic approach in which both academia and industry capabilities are effectively exploited
<i>Industry needs to make long-term planning</i>		May be frustrated by the common uncertainties of early stage scientific developments
<i>Specification documents not mature for production</i>	Identification of outstanding R&D activities can create opportunities for the involvement of companies with fair remuneration	Companies may be forced to modify the design by using internal resources with no recognition of the work done
External factors	Opportunities	Threats
<i>Procurement legislation</i>	Initial analysis performed in AMICI seems to indicate that, at European level, new instruments like PCP and Innovation Partnerships can overcome the lock-in related constraints. This conclusion holds in the analysis carried out in this work	Provisions to avoid lock-in may discourage a company from participating to both the R&D and production phases, thus jeopardizing the possible industrial interest

<i>Procurement contractual terms</i>	PCP and Innovation procurements can provide additional flexibility. Some BSO seem to have ways of adapting, under fair and legal terms, the contractual conditions during the execution of the tender, thus increasing the flexibility.	Not sufficient flexibility to cope with uncertainties and risk that are inherent in the R&D work
<i>Practical implementation of innovative instruments</i>	The representative example of QUACO. This successful PCP can encourage further implementations	Limited experience so far may discourage implementations. Large administrative complexity. May require modifications of the rules in International Organizations.
<i>Current trend in enhancing cooperation among BSO (Big Science Organizations and communities)</i>	Experience in one BSO can be exploited in others; there are concrete indications that experience in other sectors like space and fusion might be useful. Coordinated planning of R&D activities in common sectors may enhance the industry participation	Significant difficulties to find resources for such expansion of capabilities. It cannot be done with marginal resources.
<i>ASc&T community aims to organize its strategy at long-term</i>	A more suitable scenario to encourage industry to define innovation capability and resources	
<i>Poor or non-existing cooperation among industrial companies</i>		Companies may not be able to bring their needs to the attention of the ASc&T community with the necessary efficacy
<i>Emphasis on governments and EC to support the R&D activities in the companies</i>	Participation in R&D activities is considered an import enabling factor for the development of the industrial innovation potential	A clear integral strategy is mandatory for the success of R&D funding programs in industry. Significant resources and a solid managerial structure needed. Risk of reduction of technology diversity.

Table 3. SWOT analysis of early engagement of industry in R&D activities

5.4 POSSIBLE ACTIONS TO EXTEND THE INVOLVEMENT OF THE INDUSTRY ON ASc&T ACTIVITIES

From Table 3, the following specific actions can be identified to discuss with the research institutions and industry as specific actions to advance in the next years, eventually under other research projects

run by the Accelerator Science and Technology community to address a more advanced research infrastructures-industry approach at early stages or low TRLs.

Possible actions to promote from the Research Institutions

1. Related to actions internal in the ASc&T community:

- 1.1. **Leverage the internal technological capacity of prototyping** in line with the existing industry. Or, in the wording used in D5.5 of AMICI: agree a formulation for the *Subsidiary Principle*.
- 1.2. **Promote Education and Training programs of real interest to the industry**, in coordination with the industry.
- 1.3 **Promote the integration, classification and distribution of information** on new initiatives, calls, projects, infrastructure upgrades, etc.
- 1.4 **Assure long-term development plans.**

2. Actions related to the coordination with other communities:

- 2.1 Promote the **integration of roadmaps within synergetic communities**. Join strategies on ASc&T specific subjects.
- 2.2 **Impulse synergies with other Big Science fields**, in particular Fusion and Space, which might help to avoid peak-valley activity gaps.

3. Related to contract rules:

- 3.1. **Reconsider the liability and required guarantees** in contracts when working at early stages.
- 3.2 Use and **expand innovation procurement procedures**.
- 3.3 Promote **flexible conditions in procurement contracts**.
- 3.4 Work with the funding agencies to advance on **funding tools to the industry specific for R&D**.
- 3.5 R&D Funding programs focused to industry

Possible actions to promote by the industry

4. Organizational aspects:

- 4.1 Increase **self-organization within the industry**. Industry associations must be encouraged.
- 4.2. Strengthen the **relationship with the Research Institutions**, being proactive in the ASc&T strategic development plans.
- 4.3. Proactivity on **E&T programs** (interdisciplinary interchanges, industrial PhD programs, ...)
- 4.4 The creation of **permanent industry-academia fora**.

5. Investment and risk strategy:

- 5.1. Help to **co-fund** the needed investment, at a fair balance, depending on the distance to the market.
- 5.2. **Invest further resources for earlier stages** to orientate the vision of the design and development with higher market impact.
- 5.3. Promote mechanisms to **share the risk**.

6 Introductory study of procurement procedures

6.1 FLEXIBLE CONDITIONS IN THE PROCUREMENT CONTRACTS

One of the points in Section 5 that deserved specific attention to us was the interest to promote flexible conditions in the procurement contracts (3.3).

A specific recommendation to extend the use and expand innovation procurement procedures was collected from the interaction with the industry (3.2). Pre-Commercial and Innovation Procurements has arisen clear expectations in the last years and, to our opinion, have been already identified as suitable tools for early engagement.

Besides innovation procurements, we have tried to understand whether the reluctancy detected on some interviews about the use of ordinary procurement procedures for a proper innovation approach with the industry is actually based on solid arguments or instead it is a wrong interpretation due to a partial knowledge of the procurement procedures.

6.2 PRE-COMMERCIAL AND INNOVATION PROCUREMENTS

Pre-commercial and innovation procurements have been widely promoted in the last years for purchasing components with high level of innovation. We confirm that the use of these innovation tools for procurement, although not as extensively used as ideally expected, must be consolidated in the next research projects both at European and national levels, since they are some of the most suitable tools for early coordination with industry, maintaining acceptable conditions in terms of IP share, reasonable economic conditions for the industry at stages far from the market and very flexible conditions.

Despite the confirmation of the suitability of Pre-Commercial and innovation procurements for early stage interactions, some relevant constraints limiting an extended use of them must be pointed out. Among them:

- Administrative complexity to set out and track the procurement must be reconsidered with funding agencies and legal governmental departments in the next iterations. In particular when procurement rules do not allow multistage procurement with prequalification, best value for money criteria or options to invest or subsidize tooling.
- Some economic conditions in these contracts have been identified as limiting factors by the industry. Specifically, aspects related to guarantee (too high for prototypes or first-of-a-kind developments) and limiting cash flow (late partial payments and reduced pre-payments) must seriously reviewed.
- An excessive cost for the projects due to the need to fund more than one first and second stages. Although this mechanism may promote the creation of competitiveness, imposing this formula on every contract instead of allowing the 1-1-1 formula may be a limitation in some projects.

However, PCPs allow reducing global financial risks for companies as i) they are paid for the development of a new technology, ii) the production means can be partially financed by the PCP and iii) the risk of underestimating the cost of a first of a kind prototype is reduced as the company was involved in the conceptual and development phases.

6.3 CONVENTIONAL PROCUREMENTS FOR R&D PURCHASING

Apart from innovation procurements, in this work we have been motivated to understand whether ordinary procurement procedures already existing are sufficient for a proper innovation approach with the industry, or if it is a real limiting factor as it has been commented in some cases. Since a deep study of this point is out of the scope of this work, we have carried on a first study on standard procurement procedures.

For such, we have placed a contract with an expert company [9] with the aim of analyzing the use of this type of contracts in some representative countries in Europe. The analysis was based on contract files from CIEMAT, INFN, CEA, STFC and the Universities of Lund and Uppsala, as representative centers from Spain, Italy, France, the UK and Sweden. Four contract files from each institution above were analyzed.

In conclusion, the analysis reveals a common approach towards flexibility in the execution of public contracts. Despite the differences in procurement regulations and procedures, they all start from the same European Directives, so similar characteristics are identified that promote adaptability to changing needs.

Tools such as functional specifications, the ability to propose modifications and alternatives, and the prioritization, in most cases of value judgment criteria, have been demonstrated useful to adapt to complex technical projects and efficient for fostering innovation and ensuring the delivery of optimal results if managed adequately. They are recommended to be adopted in early-stage procurement processes.

Further details of this study can be found in Annex IV.

7 Analysis of the factors and actions identified

7.1 ANALYSIS WITHIN AIPF

The list outlined in Section 5.4 is an extensive compilation of possible actions and factors to address a more advanced research infrastructures-industry approach at low TRLs, but it is very difficult to consider in full. In order to provide an efficient outcome of this work, a prioritization is needed.

For such prioritization, after an internal analysis, we did not consider advisable to carry out a second general iteration with the industry. It took a significant effort for the industry to complete the first iteration, and we feared that they would not react with the same proactivity to a second round. (This was the reason to remove the task 4.1 from the Work Plan in Section 2.5.)

A high level body of industry representatives would be ideal for this discussion. But, as identified in 2.3.1, at the time of starting this work, there were not such body to interact with the industry target of our study.

Due to this motivation and other needs from the ASc&T community for a suitable contact with the industry, from WP3.3 we decided to promote the creation of a permanent industry accelerator board. In June 2023, the *Accelerator Industry Permanent Forum* was created under the umbrella of the

TIARA consortium, with the mission of bringing together the industry and the Accelerator Science and Technology community beyond specific projects, to foster a coordinated approach in advancing knowledge, increase integrated innovation capacities and addressing together societal challenges.

One of the main missions of AIPF that we suggested was to outline strategies to remove obstacles that limit the optimal exploitation of the synergistic cooperation between industry and RI&TI, in line with our main role in WP3.3.

Once the AIPF board created, an interaction with this board was considered as the most suitable option to conclude the analysis of this work.

7.2 THE PRIORITIES AMONG THE PROPOSED ACTIONS

The AIPF was constituted articulated in two subgroups: the Industry and Research Institutions subgroups. We interacted with the two subgroup leaders regarding the actions identified in Section 5.4. After that, the two co-chairs submitted a questionnaire to the corresponding subgroups and concluded the work with two on-line meetings (December 12 and 14, 2023), conducted to discuss the outcome of the survey and conclude some final prioritized recommendations.

The results of the feedback received are outlined in Table 4 below. The results are divided in three subsets, corresponding to replies from industry members, RI members and the two ILO representatives (integrated in the two subgroups), for the 5 selected sub-categories in the list in Section 5.4.

1. Possible actions to be promoted by the Research Institutions

1. Internal actions within the AS&T community				
	TOTAL	IND	LAB	ILO
1.1. Leverage the internal technological capacity of prototyping in line with the existing industry	4.1	3.8	4.3	4
Promote Education and Training programs of real interest to the industry	3.9	3.4	4.7	3.5
1.2 Promote the integration, classification and distribution of information on new initiatives, calls, projects, infrastructure upgrades, etc.	4.4	4.6	4.3	4
1.3 Assure long-term development plans	4.3	3.8	4.3	5
2. Actions associated with coordinating efforts with other communities				
	TOTAL	IND	LAB	ILO
2.1 Promote the integration of roadmaps within synergetic communities	4.4	4.4	3.7	5
2.2 Impulse synergies with other Big Science fields, in particular Fusion and Space	4.0	3.6	3.7	5
3. Actions regarding contract rules				
	TOTAL	IND	LAB	ILO

3.1 Reconsider the liability and required guarantees in contracts when working at early stages	3.8	3.2	3.7	5
3.2 Use and expand innovation procurement procedures	4.0	3.8	3.7	5
3.3 Promote flexible conditions in procurement contracts	4.0	3.8	4.0	4.5
3.4 Work with the funding agencies to advance on funding tools to the industry specific for R&D	4.1	3.6	4.7	4
3.5.R&D Funding programs focused to industry	4.4	4.4	4.7	4

2. Possible actions to be promoted by the Industry

4. Organizational aspects				
	TOTAL	IND	LAB	ILO
4.1 Increase self-organization within the industry. Industry associations must be encouraged.	3.7	3	4.3	4
4.2. Strengthen the relationship with the Research Institutions, being proactive in the ASc&T strategic development plans	4.2	3.8	4.7	4.5
4.3. Proactivity on E&T programs (interdisciplinary interchanges, industrial PhD programs, ...)	3.7	3.2	4.7	3.5
4.4. The creation of permanent industry-academia fora	4.4	4.6	4.3	3.5

5. Investment and risk strategy				
	TOTAL	IND	LAB	ILO
5.1. Help to co-fund the needed investment, at a fair balance, depending on the distance to the market	4.0	4.2	3.7	3.5
5.2. Invest further resources for earlier stages to orientate the vision of the design and development with higher market impact	3.5	3.6	3.3	3.5
5.3. Promote mechanisms to share the risk	3.9	4.4	3.0	4

Table 4. Recommendations considered by the AIPF with priority for the 5 selected sub-categories, ranged from 0 (no priority) to 5 (highest priority). In red, the highest score identified on each subgroup.

It is noteworthy that in the evaluation given by the AIPF survey to the actions listed in 5.4, all them were rated over 3.0 (in a range of 0.0-5.0) by industry, research institutions and ILOs representatives, except one of them. Surprisingly, the industry representatives did not give higher priority to the action 4.1 (*Increase self-organization within the industry. Industry associations must be encouraged*). A possible cause for this feedback may be the reluctancy of the collective for the actual capability to build this kind of associations at European level.

In the survey submitted by the two AIPF co-chairs, it was asked about any action not listed in the survey that could be important for facilitating an early industry-research institutions engagement. The feedback received are discussed in the section below.

7.3 MISSING POINTS INDICATED BY AIPF

To the consultation addressed to AIPF about any action not listed in the survey that could be important for facilitating an early industry-research institution engagement, only two comments were provided:

- Explore accelerator industrial applications, recognizing areas demanding innovation and specific technologies.
- Investment in mechanisms for risk identification related to particular TRLs and recognition of risk taking by each of the contributing partners.

Our considerations to this feedback are the following:

1. There are no major comments from industry, research infrastructures and ILOs representatives to the list of topics identified in Section 5.4.
2. There exists an interest in the industry for the ASc&T community to explore further industrial applications. In other words, the interest for promoting other applications apart for basic Science.
3. Risk sharing is a major concern for the industry. Although this point was introduced in our list, we receive a clear indication that it must further developed, in particular the different understanding of the TRL and risk associated to it.

8 Conclusions and Considerations

8.1 CONSIDERATIONS TO UNDERSTAND THE OUTCOME OF THIS WORK

This work has made an effort to compile a detailed collection of opinions and ideas to promote an early engagement of industry and research institutions in the Accelerator Science and Technology field. These ideas were discussed specifically with a representative number of industries and research institutions, and also with some national ILO office members. Specific attention was paid to their particular experiences and needs. In this way, the input collected can be considered as relative complete feedback from the industrial collective.

The first relevant consideration to the results of the interaction with the industry is the heterogeneity of their feedback. The industrial collective members consulted are very different in terms of dimension and scope and, more important for our work, with very different experience of collaboration with research institutions and with different level of information of our research environment.

In line with this, we note that it has been difficult to obtain a coherent short list of prioritized messages from the industry.

A second consideration that we point out is the relevant difference of vision between industry and research institutions about how to approach a closer collaboration at early stages. This has been clearly identified in the results outlined in Table 4.

8.2 THE NEED TO PROMOTE A BETTER INTERNAL COORDINATION

From the comments above, a first global output from this work is the following:

***Recommendation 1:** Previous to any other relevant action, a better mutual knowledge within the industry collective itself and between this and research institutions is a major need. Discussion bodies to facilitate long-term discussions and create a common language are necessary. Without this step, any continuation of this work will face the risk of repeating similar uncertainties (heterogeneous feedback).*

In this context, the promotion and support of the creation of an Accelerator Industry Permanent Forum is a relevant outcome. WP3.3 contributed significantly to declare its importance, to promote it within the TIARA consortium and to initiate its activities. But we anticipate that the creation of an industrial board is not the most complex step: it will take a strong effort to make it operative and consolidate it.

***Recommendation 2:** A relevant effort must be carried out by the community to provide resources to sustain and make operative an accelerator industry board, to become a reliable entry point to the industry. Specifically, this recommendation could be focused to the AIPF recently constituted.*

8.3 ABOUT THE PROCUREMENT CONTRACTING RULES

One last consideration is related to the procurement contract procedures. During this work, the idea of the need for more flexible rules in the contract procedures related innovation was addressed by some industries and research institutions. To better understand this point as a possible aspect to work further, it was carried out a short-range study, analyzing standard procurement rules in a number of representative countries in Europe. The results achieved does not reflect that an action to modify existing rules for contracting may be a major need for a suitable innovation environment at low TRLs. Instead, a deeper knowledge and a proper use of the existing procedures should be recommendable.

In spite of the consideration above, specific points related to contract procedures arose during our conversations with the industry as possible sources of risk for the companies. Although it cannot be considered as a general need, a request sent from specific companies was related to reconsider the liability and required guarantees in contracts when working at early stages. Similarly, the cash flow pressure for the small companies in medium-large contracts should be subject to review in future works.

***Recommendation 3:** Encourage in next activities to exploit in full the tools available in the contract procedures to facilitate the innovation processes. The use of innovation procurement is encouraged, but not in all cases these procurement formats are needed. Standard contracts may also offer rules for award and follow up useful to guarantee the flexibility that the contracts involving innovation demand.*

In any case, it should be advisable to analyze the liability terms, required guarantees and distribution of partial payments in contracts when involving SMES at early stages.

8.4 PROPOSALS FOR PRIORITIZED ACTIONS

We listed in Section 5.4 the actions proposed to explore for advancing to a closer industry-research institution approach at early stages. In the last review of these actions (Section 7.2), practically all the actions listed in 5.4 were rated over 3.0 (in a range of 0.0-5.0) by industry, research institutions and ILOs representatives in the Accelerator Industry Permanent Forum.

In the last analysis, we could only identify two missing actions to consider, outlined in Section 7.3. The most important one was related to the need of exploring accelerator industrial applications.

Recommendation 4: *Explore and promote accelerator industrial applications, beyond basic Science.*

This message is in clear coherence with the strategy expressed by the ASc&T community to address both at short and medium ranges in their future actions and roadmaps.

If we consider the proposed actions evaluated over 4.0 in the survey as the most important actions identified, a list of 12 actions is obtained.

This list of 12 prioritized actions is the list recommended in this work for future projects and roadmaps (Table 5.1):

Recommended Prioritized Action	Subgroup
3.5. R&D Funding programs focused to industry	RI 3. Actions regarding contract rules
2.1. Promote the integration of roadmaps within synergetic communities	RI 2. Actions associated with coordinating efforts with other communities
1.3. Assure long-term development plans	RI 1. Internal actions within the ASc&T community
1.2. Promote the integration, classification and distribution of information on new initiatives, calls, projects, infrastructure upgrades, etc.	RI 1. Internal actions within the ASc&T community
4.2. Strengthen the relationship with the Research Institutions, being proactive in the ASc&T strategic development plans	Industry 4. Organizational aspects
3.2. Use and expand innovation procurement procedures	RI 3. Actions regarding contract rules
4.4. The creation of permanent industry-academia fora	Industry 4. Organizational aspects
3.3. Promote flexible conditions in procurement contracts	RI 3. Actions regarding contract rules
3.4. Work with the funding agencies to advance on funding tools to the industry specific for R&D	RI 3. Actions regarding contract rules
2.2. Impulse synergies with other Big Science fields, in particular Fusion and Space	2. Actions associated with coordinating efforts with other communities
1.1. Leverage the internal technological capacity of prototyping in line with the existing industry	RI 1. Internal actions within the ASc&T community
3.1. Reconsider the liability and required guarantees in contracts when working at early stages	RI 3. Actions regarding contract rules

Table 5.1. The list of 12 prioritized actions recommended in WP3.3.

From the evaluation in Section 7.2., we identify that Table 5.1. misses some fundamental comments provided by the industry. If we consider the actions evaluated by the industry with a rate over 4.0, we

identify six actions. Among these six, only 4 of them are listed in Table 5.1 (marked in blue). Considering the importance of the specific feedback of the industry in this study, we would recommend to take into account also the other two, namely, the ones listed in Table 5.2 below.

Recommended Prioritized Action (specifically by the Industry)	Subgroup
5.3. Promote mechanisms to share the risk	Industry 5. Investment and risk strategy
5.1. Help to co-fund the needed investment, at a fair balance, depending on the distance to the market	Industry 5. Investment and risk strategy

Table 5.2. The two items prioritized by the industry to complement the actions in Table 5.1.

The two actions in Table 5.2. are related to the demand raised by industry to analyze mechanisms to share the risk taken by the industry at early stages.

8.5 SUMMARY OF CONCLUSIONS

8.5.1 Recommendations

1. Previous to any other relevant action, better mutual knowledge within the industry collective itself and between industry and research institutions is a major need. Discussion bodies to facilitate long-term discussions and create a common language are relevant. Without this step, any other continuation of this work will carry with the risk of repeating similar uncertainties.
2. In the scope above, a relevant effort must be carried out by the community to provide resources to sustain and make operative an accelerator industry board, to become a reliable entry point to the industry. Specifically, this recommendation could be focused to the AIPF recently constituted.
3. Encourage in next activities to exploit in full the tools available in the contract procedures to facilitate the innovation processes. The use of innovation procurement is encouraged, but not in all cases these procurement formats are needed. Standard contracts may also offer rules for award and follow up useful to guarantee the flexibility that the contracts involving innovation demand. In any case, it should be advisable to analyze the liability terms, required guarantees and distribution of partial payments in contracts when involving SMES at early stages.
4. Explore and promote accelerator industrial applications beyond basic Science.
This recommendation is being already integrated by the ASc&T community on its strategy both at short (in the proposals under preparation) and medium ranges (the preparation for the HE WP 2025-2027).

8.5.2 Prioritized actions to promote

If we summarize the main prioritized actions result of the analysis of this work, taking into account the considerations above and unifying similarities, the outcome is the following (in parenthesis, the action number in the list in Section 5.4 and Tables 4, 5.1 and 5.2):

Related to Financial aspects

- Promote R&D funding programs focused to industry (3.5)
- Promote mechanisms to share the risk (5.3)
- Help to co-fund the needed investment, at a fair balance, depending on the distance to the market (5.1)
- Reconsider the liability and required guarantees in contracts when working at early stages (3.1)

Related to contract procedures

- Use and expand innovation procurement procedures (3.2)
- Further exploit the capability of conventional procurement procedures for innovation

Related to expand the coordination with other communities

- Promote the integration of roadmaps within synergetic communities (2.1)
- Impulse synergies with other Big Science fields, in particular Fusion and Space (2.2)

Related to internal coordinated actions

- Assure long-term development plans (1.3)
- Promote the integration, classification and distribution of information on new initiatives, calls, projects, infrastructure upgrades, etc. (1.2)
- Leverage the internal technological capacity of prototyping in line with the existing industry (1.1)
- Strengthen the relationship with the Research Institutions, being proactive in the ASc&T strategic development plans (4.2)
- The creation of permanent industry-academia fora (4.4)²

None of the actions listed above are simple, nor implementable at a short-range without a strong commitment of the whole community. Some of them may be controversial, since they can affect to the internal strategy of research institutions (e.g., 1.1) and may represent an effort difficult to accomplish without implementing specific plans that will demand funds and resources.

In this context, the ideas collected and discussed in this work may represent a valuable reference for incoming initiatives, both for specific developments and for wider roadmaps of the accelerator science and technology community.

² In this list:

Action 3.3. *Promote flexible conditions in procurement contracts* has been removed as outcome of this work;

Action 3.4. *Work with the funding agencies to advance on funding tools to the industry specific for R&D*, although not identical, have been absorbed in 3.5.

9 References

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10 Annex I. List of key questions

IFAST Project. WP3, Task 3. Industry-Academia approach at early stages.

Interview with companies. Key Questions

General points

- From your experience of collaboration with research institutes, please, comment on your vision about an efficient industry-research center interaction. In particular, the added value of a collaboration at early stages.
- Please, comment on the key drivers for the pros and cons of an early stage collaboration with research institutes.
- Please, comment if you see any possibility to really get the common competences and capabilities (both of the industry and academia) exploited better

Specific subjects

1. Funding tools for a better industry-academia approach at early stages.

1.1. CE/National Program calls:

- Examples of call formats benefiting this approach
- Examples of call formats not benefiting this approach
- Please, define your ideal CE-MS funding programs for such approach.

1.2. Type of procurement/contracting rules.

- Procurement contracts at national level. Drawbacks
- Focused tenders. Pros and cons
- Collaboration vs procurement
- The ideal tender processes

2. Timing

2.1. Which is the right moment to initiate the industry-academia contacts?

- On development projects. From existing prototypes to series
- On R&D projects. From the starting of the initiative
- Risk and advantages of early contacts

3. Research Strategy

3.1. From the point of view of the interest of the industry,

- How do you see the dissemination of the overall strategy of the projects, from the H2020 projects, communities, task force groups ...?

3.2. More in detail about the access to information of new projects

- Preliminary Meetings.
- User/Suppliers project meeting in advance to CDR.

3.3. In a similar focus. Please, comment on your vision about how industry can find the right information for a suitable collaboration on the projects. In two scenarios:

- Large collaboration projects, like IFAST
- Bilateral actions, few partners projects, directly led or supported by a research institution

4. Market and competition issues

- 4.1. Pros and cons about early contacts from the commercial point of view.
- 4.2. How to handle fair competition at early stages
- 4.3. How to handle the risk of an early engagement.
- 4.4. How to pin focus on market since the early beginning.

5. Education, training, outreach

- 5.1. Tools to get access to the suitable knowledge. Needed further tools?
- 5.2. Tools for personnel interchange: EU projects, infrastructures programs, collaborations with Academia ...
Needed further tools?

6. IP.

- 6.1. Patent model:
 - Previous patents and owned by one single party
 - Co-generated patents
- 6.2. Alternatives to the patent model

7. ILO / TT Offices / Industrial Associations

- 7.1. The roles of ILO/TT Offices / Industrial Associations. Feedback
- 7.2. The roles of the Framework projects (ARIES). Feedback
- 7.3. The roles of the Community collaborations (TIARA, LEAPS). Feedback

9. Network and links

- 8.1. To the eye of the industry: is the network of research institutions in Europe efficient?
- 8.2. Is it there a clearly identifiable unique body Industry/Lab to Brussels?
- 8.3. How do you see the existing links with other communities such as LEAPS, detectors?
- 8.4. How do you see the existing links among different fields (Space, PP, Fusion, medical, ...)?

11 Annex II. Interaction with Industry. Preliminary considerations

IFAST Project. WP3.3. Considerations about early engagement of the industry on Accelerator Activities

II.1. Key aspects

Points to consider to promote an industry-Research Institutions interaction at low TRL within the ASc&T sector

Specific considerations

- Involve the industry on research activity from the design stage.
- Separate the design stage from the production stage.
- Involve the final user since the very early beginning.
- The good relationship with research institutions is considered as a strong added value. A work program based on the trust, on solid relations, is a base for success. This simplifies tremendously the IP concerns.
- A limitation: the involvement of the industry in a collaboration with the research institution before placing the contract can generate conflict of interests. Providing support to the research institutions at early stages is in some cases considered as a non-equity advantage for applying to the tender.
- Early engagement is good for an adequate IP management. The IP generation, when addressed at high TRL models, is not ideal to the industry.
- Some companies declare as critical point to have limited liability. Liability cannot be unlimited; it is a blocking point to the companies. Engaging at low TRL can facilitate this point

Strategy

- Pursue well defined research and development programs, with integrated aims.
- A strategy coordinated with the industry: the objectives defined according with the resources of the research institutions and the resources and capability of the industry, put in common. The growing plan defined together. Joining strategies.
- Prepare the industrial ecosystem at longer terms. Face the "peaks and valleys" on the demands for research developments.
- Revision of the IP strategy.
- Explore synergies with other fields: expand the demands from ASc&T in coordination with other Big Science fields.
- A better internal organization among the industrial community, helping to create a coordinated strategy. It is not only the academia the ones who has to mobilize towards a common direction.

Education and training

- Support for training of young expert engineers and scientists. Sharing training personnel between research institutions and industry. Sharing the costs
- It is important the training personnel to be in the industry, at least partially.

Procurement procedures

- Among the options available on procurements, only innovative procurements such as PCP are mentioned as a model well suited to work at low TRL.
- Use and expand innovation procurement procedures.

- Follow successful examples in other fields, more advanced: Space in particular. Fusion in some aspects.

I.2. Actions to analyze for promoting collaboration at low TRL

Research institutions

- Research Institutions have to avoid prototyping internally in some aspects or, at least, not alone.
- IP must be shared since the early beginning. Tender processes must be adapted to this strategy.
- Leverage our internal technological capacity in line with the existing industry.
- Insisting on promoting efficient E&T programs, making them visible to industry with lower experience and contacts via ILO.
- Assuring long-term development plans.
- Related to the previous point: guarantee the access to the information on new initiatives, calls, projects, infrastructure upgrades, etc, under a coordinated scheme.
- Include the industry on the ASc&T strategy: the objectives defined according with the resources of the research institutions and the resources and capability of the industry, put in common.
- Promote the integration of roadmaps within synergetic communities. Join strategies specifically on ASc&T.
- Promote synergies with other Big Science fields. In particular, Fusion and Space, that might help to avoid peak-valley activity gaps. (*)
- Promote flexible conditions in the procurement contracts.
- Use and expand innovation procurement procedures. Relevant examples in other fields.

The industry

- A major effort on self-organization. Industry associations must be encouraged.
- Being proactive in the information about projects and tenders. Via conferences, sharing research projects (in particular the transversal work packages of integration projects, or via ILOs, among others).
- Help to co-fund the needed investment, at a fair balance, depending on the distance to the market.
- Proactivity on Education and Training programs (interdisciplinary interchanges, industrial PhD programs, ...)
- Further resources since earlier stages to orientate the vision of development and singular equipment with higher market impact.
- Be ready to share risk.
- Simplify and speed-up the internal communication process and the flux of information (catalogs, list of contacts, ...)

II.2. Summary on main aspects addressed

1. Facts affecting the analysis

The industry working on the production of components or solutions for the Accelerator sector is very heterogeneous. For this reason, we should not expect a unified message from this community.

There are two main reasons why the industry gets involved in the technologies needed by the accelerator sector (ASc&T). They could aim for:

- series productions to reach the general market and/or
- the production of specific products for the Scientific Infrastructures (one-shot).

There are also two relation mechanisms:

- Procurement via contracts and
- collaboration in projects.

In both cases, not all industries accept or get motivated by both options.

Differences are not only related to the relation the industry has with the research institutions but also to the intrinsic nature of the companies, their involvement in the sector or the resources available. Here are some of these differences:

- **ASc&T activity rate:** From 20% to 80-100%.
- **Knowledge of the field:** Some companies are just informed via closer institutions, while others invest heavily in collecting information via conferences and face-to-face meetings among others.
- **Funding rate required versus potential benefit:** A combination of factors, related to the added value in terms of intellectual return to the company or the distance to the market or the availability of resources, among others that is not the same in every company.

Finally, the industry involved in ASc&T seems not to be a very consolidated, well-organized community.

2. The global opinion of the industry on a deeper involvement on Low TRL

Most interviewed companies are in strong favor of being involved at low TRL. They think that it is beneficial for both sides. However:

- The concept of early engagement **is not perfectly agreed upon by all companies**. In most cases, it is understood that “involvement in Low TRL” means starting a contractual relationship with the research institution from the conceptual design phase.
- Companies with wider experience indicate that **adequate information on the future needs of the product is required** as they can/have to build a business plan that will be based on this information.
- A number of companies with longer experience in the field **criticize strongly the current model**, claiming that a different approach closer to the “*old times*” is required.
- Smaller industries, limit their interest to some aspects, mainly due to a **lack of resources** and not being open to investing significant resources for their involvement in low TRL projects.

As a co-lateral remark, we received two messages

- It is a good praxis involving to the final buyer early on the industry/academia collaboration, when this is not the research institution in charge of the development.
- Companies find big difficulties on the last steps to the market. Regulation and legal aspects are a severe burden to them, with a reduced help from institutions and specialized companies.

3. The ideal industry-research labs interaction model within the ASc&T sector

From the feedback of the industries, we identify that, in the fields in which the research institutions could work with industry at low TRL and the institution decide not to do it, somehow, the research institution becomes a competitor of the industry. **The procurer can become a competitor.**

If going to a higher level of integration of the industry at low TRL, the model demanded by the most experienced industry would suit the following points:

- Involve the company **from the design stage**.
- **Involve the final user** from the very early beginning.
- Pursue **well-defined research and development programs**, with integrated aims and long-term objectives.
- **Separate the design stage from the production stage**.
- Have a work program based on **trust and on a solid relationship**. This simplifies tremendously the IP concerns.

Some other crucial points beyond the interaction model:

- **A strategy coordinated with the industry**: the objectives defined according with the resources of the research institutions and the resources and capability of the industry, put in common. A growing plan defined together. Joining strategies.
- **Prepare the industrial ecosystem at longer terms**. Face the "peaks and valleys" of the demands for research developments.
- **Support for the training of young expert engineers and scientists**. Sharing training personnel between research institutions and industry. Sharing the costs
- On this last issue, it is important that the **personnel involved in the training can work in the industry**, at least partially.
- Use and expand **innovation procurement procedures**. Relevant examples in other fields.

4. The case of not working at low TRL

Some relevant companies declare cases in which the research institutions in the ASc&T field keep the policy of covering by themselves the first stages of the technological research, developing its own first prototypes. When this is the case:

- **Technical Suboptimization**: The result is not optimum from the final technical outcome viewpoint; the industry claims that prototypes developed in this format, in many cases, are subject to foregoing improvements as they are not industrialized, and the techniques used are not always the ones that industry will use.
- **Cost suboptimization**: Procurements based on prototypes developed by the research institutions alone are subject to limitations that can affect the contract development itself. Prototypes subject to improvements mean modification of specifications, longer delivery terms and larger costs. Technologies can also be more costly or difficult to use for mass production.
- **Risk moved to the industry**: Using techniques that are not the optimal ones for industrialization will have a cost. Industries will face the dilemma of quoting what it is requesting knowing that will fail and that then they will have to face potential over costs or risk of losing the tender. In some cases, the conclusion is that the company decides to accept the contract without a budget for contingencies for changes that are, in the end, needed.
- **Conflict of interest**. Providing support to the research institutions at early stages was considered a non-equity advantage for applying to the tender.
- Early engagement is good for **an adequate IP management**. The IP generation, when engaged at high TRL models, is not ideal to the industry.

5. What else we can do to promote a low TRL approach

In order to deploy an advanced low TRL research institutions-industry collaboration program in ASc&T, some actions can be foreseen to carry on from the research institutions and industry.

Actions from the research institutions

In the topics in which we decide start working at low TRL, **changes must be done within the research institutions to adapt our activity to this model:**

- **Avoid prototyping internally when the feasibility of the component/equipment is not put in doubt by the industry.**
- **Share IP since the early beginning.** The IP generation, when engaged at high TRL models, is not ideal for the industry.
- **Adapt the tender processes** so as to be able to buy R&D produced with the industry and not just components.

Actions from both:

The following general concepts are more relevant at low TRL:

- A strategy coordinated with the industry: the objectives must be defined according with the resources of the research institutions and the resources and capability of the industry, put in common.
- Well defined research and development programs, with integrated aims and long term.
- More proactivity on setting a long-term strategy with the industry.
- Proactivity on Education and Training programs for stays both at research labs and industry.
- Avoid peak-valley activity gaps. Increase the dimension range. Create integrated industrial plans. Trying to find synergies with other fields. In particular, Fusion and Space.
- The growing plan defined together. Joining strategies.
- A better internal organization among the industrial community, helping to create a coordinated strategy. It is not only the academia the ones who has to mobilize towards a common direction.

6. About tendering and partnership tools to promote low TRL

Current procurements and project partnership models

As previously indicated, there are two relation mechanisms:

- Procurement via contracts and
- collaboration in projects.

Procurements in the ASc&T sector are not a strong source of revenue.

Collaborations and Partnerships on research projects are seen mainly as a method to:

- **gain expertise;**
- **gain a recognized reference;**
- **establish close links** with research institutions, and
- invest in **know-how**.

They consider it as an investment and, for such, they accept the co-fund that this partnership implies.

Specific messages received

- Separate the tender in steps.
- A good tendering strategy: the institution places an order for a preliminary study and then, to avoid problem of the competition during the tender, the institution owns the intellectual property produced.
- The rules must be clear. Avoid too many options, it is limiting, in term of costs. More options mean that the company has to look for protections.

Having said that, they highlight that there are no golden rules.

Limitations reported

Often research institutions request **quotations for a concept based on schematic drawings**. This can be misleading as many times the design must be adapted before the development stage towards industrial specifications. It also consumes industrial resources.

Before the contract, the risk for the company is that the discussions with the institution are started in many cases providing know-how in advance, modifying the design, with no guarantee of being awarded. The company may invest its time and know-how to improve a design that other company may win. From the industrial point of view, this procedure discourages from sharing information with the research projects. They report that this happens quite frequently.

In many cases, accelerators, synchrotrons and other related facilities provides designs not completely finalized. And, from this step, budget quotations are requested. Some companies do not just offer their help for improving the specifications; they simply go to the tender. But, in the tender, the design is frozen and, if not optimized, the product is less reliable, more expensive.

Most of the times, research institutions want to have the most modern instrumentation for their experiments. Sometimes this goes against the reliability of the final product: the most advance instrument cannot be the most reliable. It can turn into a product that cannot be reliable.

Liability

Some companies declare as critical point to have limited liability. Liability cannot be unlimited; it is a blocking point to the companies, to the limit that, sometimes, they have been excluded from some tenders due to this aspect.

Comparison with other regions

Very experienced companies report that, if we compare the contract procedures in Europe with those in ASIA, Canada, USA, they do not find too much difference; they are very much comparable. Same level of specifications, rules bit different (USA: easier best value for money), but not significantly.

From this message, they infer that, regarding standard procurement contracts, there is no much room for improvement in Europe; not much if compared with other countries.

Regarding collaboration and not tendering, the USA has the SBIR3 and STTR programs that target among others “Foster technology transfer through cooperative R&D between small businesses and research institutions”. These programs target common R&D between SMEs and research institutions and are fully funded by the US Government to stimulate technological innovation and multisector collaboration.

Successful tendering processes

Among the options discussed on procurements, only innovative procurements such as PCPs are mentioned as a model well suited to work at low TRL. The PCPs are procurement contracts targeting engineering services and follow the concept of the best value for money. They also consider that material and tooling could remain with the companies if this enhances their capabilities and forces a very clear IP definition from the conceptual phase.

More advanced models in other fields

Examples of tendering processes of interest to low TRL have been found in other fields. In Space applications, ESA has specific programs for low TRL: it is the case of the former TRP, currently TDE (Technology Development Element). Their vision is to secure the competitiveness of our industry. Beyond plain business, strategy for setting industry.

³ <https://www.sbir.gov/about>

ESA manages the IPR to facilitate the attractiveness to the industry. Purchasing not only to fly equipment, but to promote competition. ESA does not aim at being owners. They leave to the developers. With rights of access, free licenses for the member states.

Besides, we want to highlight that ESA has set out procurement procedures flexible enough to be adapted to modifications during the procurement phase. Procurement rules open to competition with negotiation. CCN (Contract Change Notice, ESA own regulation as International Organization): sometimes, motivated by ESA, sometimes, requested by industry.

12 Annex III. Discussions with Research and Technological Institutions

III. 1. General comments received about the work done

- The consulted RIs think that the information collected in this work is very complete. The points addressed are the fundamental topics to analyze. No relevant points missing.
- Some comments outlined are inconsistent ⁴.

III. 2. Comments about enhancing the capacity of the companies for designing and prototyping

Contradictory messages were collected in this aspect:

In favor:

- The input in the document to incorporate the industry in basic design phase to include industrialization procedures is supported by some institutions (not all).
- Example of the PCP QUACO. Industry proposed a design different to the one provided by the RI. The RI prototype resulted to be not serializable, while the industry design did.
- Industry has already resources and know how. Not needed for prototyping when the know how exists at industry. RI has to carry on with the prototyping only in the cases that the industry is unable to do it.

Against:

- The view of some RIs is that our RIs want to keep the competences of prototyping; they do not want to rely on the industry capability for its development programs.
- RIs has to secure their needs in house, because the ASc&T industry is a sector in which there are few companies, because a small market.
- There exists inherent risk if the know-how is transferred to the industry. If the company disappears, the capability is lost. Difficult to secure.
- Diversification is also a problem. No control of that.
- Developing new procedures on industry that consequently apply for a patent put a lock on the know-how.
- Early development may imply a high risk level that the industry could not afford.

III. 3. Comparison with other communities

Critical with our procedures:

- ESA procedures on industry strategy are more efficient than ours. Our RI rules are not efficient: they buy based on money. Best value for money only for services.

Protective of our procedures:

- ESA is an agency, has no competency in house. Our RIs need to keep such competences; they cannot rely on the industry capability for its development programs. The development programs must be in-house and, when the technology ready, they should be transferred.

⁴ This is expected since due to the diversity of opinions on the industrial representatives and that all these opinions were collected

III. 4. Comments about merging strategy and need with other communities

Positive:

- Synergic communities: fora like BSBF were meant for that. Further synergic actions are not needed; what it is needed is more funding resources to promote co-strategies with other R&D fields in the existing fora.
- It really depends on the field. It can be identified some niches where possible, but difficult in general. Examples of possible technical sectors for merging: electronics, high speed, short pulse, power electronics. Other fields: Energy supply, with common problems,
- Artificial Intelligence is a field with specific viable options to merge.

Negative

- Room for a more integrated approach on Big Science? It should be very interesting to merge, would benefit everyone. But it is not obvious. Severe difficulties to standardize.
- Significant difficulties to find resources for such expansion of capabilities. It cannot be done with marginal resources. In the current budget situation, the chances are very limited.

III. 5. Comments on the risk

Critic with our procedures:

- We have few large companies working for ASc&T. Big companies take no risks. Big companies do not reply our tenders because they have computed the cost of a bad prototyping from RI.
- Guarantee, cash flow, liabilities: industry cannot afford an insurance for securing liabilities. If industry develop the prototype for a RI, they cannot carry the burden of operation liability.

Protective of our procedures:

- Changes on the procedures of our large RI? Some RIs do not see this point.

III. 6. Comments on IP

Critic with our procedures:

Protective of our procedures:

- IP owned by the generator. Questionable. In the start of the PCP program, IP was not supposed to remain in the companies. It was not meant like that initially by EC.
- RIs agree on that companies should have resources, and IP. But RIs cannot leave this IP: they need this IP to place procurements, under competitive basis. RIs need to have the right to spread this IP, to guarantee competitiveness.

III. 7. Comments on funding R&D in the industry

In favor

- Grants to fund R&D in industry, non-refundable, EC programs for funding research in industry (no functional development, not even prototyping): yes, it should be a good point
- DOE programs support SMES. Money to grant experience. Non-refundable. This is our missing point. We have only the contract tool, not no-refundable funding.
- USA links the money placed on big contracts with big companies to the no- refundable fund to SMEs.

Against

- In some aspects, DOE promotes limit the standardization of own technology. Example: specific control systems only accepted by DOE. We have much more freedom in Europe, what it is positive.
- The transfer of information to use broadly the results should be difficult.

III. 8. Comments on contract procedures

Specifically, RIs are not aware of any other innovation contracts apart from PCP.

About the lack of flexibility of our contracting rules, there are discrepant views. Some RIs consider that the own standard procedures rules are fair and efficient. They must keep some level of rigidity for the sake of legality and fair procurement.

Other RIs report that, for them, research contracts are living tools. Once granted, they change into collaboration. They are able to adapt specifications and prices, up to some level. This is why they actually are research contracts. In any case, they point out that any modification must be done in a fair way, by mutual agreement (procurer-companies), to avoid disputes, and to demonstrate the use funds in an efficient way. They have regulations about how to adapt the specifications and price change. In any case, information must be clear and legal discussion must be open.

Annex IV. Details about the study on conventional procurement procedures

IV.1. Introduction and Preliminary Considerations

Ordinary procurement processes have been analyzed by the company Knowsulting⁵ regarding the application of parameters that allow changes and provides flexibility during the execution of a contract promoted by a public institution.

It must be taken into account that public procurement processes in the context of the EU are subject to the Directives of the European Parliament and of the Council 2014/23/EU and 2014/24/EU of 26 February 2014 and their respective transpositions in the respective countries, which have particular characteristics. In the case of Spain, it would be Law 9/2017, of 8th November, on Public Sector Contracts, which transposes into Spanish law the Directives of the European Parliament and of the Council 2014/23/EU and 2014/24/EU, of 26 February 2014 (the Spanish Law applicable was taken as representative of the other European State Laws in this work).

In general, contracting processes follow a progressive process of specifying the object of the contract, going from an initial determination of the need to a specific work, supply or service delivered. In the selected cases of study there are services (design, installation, configuration, testing, etc.) linked to the final definition of the supply. In the early stages of preparation of the process, the objects of the contract are usually broad and evolves according to the final requirements, the available budgets, etc., until the specification is sufficiently precise for economic operators to be able to identify the nature and scope of the procurement and decide whether to request to participate in it. At that point, the tendering procedure can be started. It can be understood that the accuracy of the information provided is not determined “by law” and may allow some flexibility during the execution. This is especially frequent in purchases that require a design and configuration service prior to supply, as is the case in the acquisition of custom-made instrumentation. Some of the tools that enables the deliberated “indetermination” of the contract object are the following:

1. The determination of the contract object by prevailing functional specification over technical specification, leaving a first larger freedom to the bidders when configuring their bids as long as the requirements are met. During the execution of the contracted works, compliance with the functional specification will take priority over the object that was "offered".
2. The way in which the execution phases of the contract and the working methodology are determined in the tender documents, starting, for example, with an initial analysis phase and/or design phase that, after validation, triggers production phase.
3. The procurement procedure chosen, highlighting those that allow a technical dialogue with the tenderers for the configuration of the offer (Negotiated Procedures) or even the object of the contract (Competitive Dialogue Procedure). In practice, this approach only allows flexibility in the tender phase.

⁵ <https://knowsulting.com/?lang=en>

In these cases, it is important to note that it is possible to pay to candidates or tenderers who have participated in the process, encouraging them to "make a best effort" in the process.

4. The identification, configuration and drafting of the evaluation criteria subject to value judgement may provide a certain amount of freedom for the evaluators to determine the most advantageous tender and the subsequent conditions of implementation. In this case, in practice, this approach allows flexibility in the award and, moreover, in the execution.
5. The admission of variants, which allow tenderers to offer alternative solutions to those prescribed in the tender specifications. In practice, this approach only allows flexibility in the tender phase since, once awarded, the chosen variant must be executed.
6. The possibility of contract modifications with impact in execution budgets. It is mandatory to foresee situations that may require modifying the conditions of the contract, up to a percentage of the award amount. It is important to take into account that unforeseen modifications are hard to justify, making it more feasible to deal with non-substantial modifications, limited to 10% of the award amount.
7. Finally, it is necessary to point out that providing flexibility during the execution of a contract has its counterpart, since it introduces risk and uncertainty. Consequently, it seems reasonable that, in order to ensure good management of public resources, the solvency criteria should be strengthened, as well as the guarantees, penalties and termination clauses.

In this study, it was analyzed how the selected contract files (see the table in IV.3) have dealt with flexibility looking for good practices and patterns to be taken into account.

IV.2. Feedback from the preliminary study on innovation and conventional procurement procedures

Contract files with the following requisites have been analyzed:

- Supply contracts or mixed service and supply contracts, the object of which is related to the purchase of scientific instrumentation in the field of particle accelerators and electromechanical engineering. Construction contracts are excluded from this analysis. It is not considered either alternatives such as concessions or financial leases (e.g. leasing) which, in our understanding, are out of the scope of this study.
- Relatively recent contract files, with publication date not older than three years.
- Contract files of high economic value, with an estimated value greater than 1,000,000.00 euros. In some cases, prioritizing the interest of the object of the contract, purchases of a lower amount have been selected.

The analysis has been based on contract files from the following centers: CIEMAT, INFN, CEA, STFC and the Universities of Lund and Uppsala.

Following the analysis of the selected contract files, various elements influencing the flexibility of contracts during their award and execution have been identified. These findings carry significant implications for enhancing the efficiency and adaptability of procurement processes in institutions. Here below we list the main conclusions obtained.

1. Functional specification and phases of contract execution

It has been identified a widespread use of functional specifications in the technical RFP (*Request for Proposals*) documents, which is crucial for providing flexibility in contract execution, allowing the contract manager to interpret the specification to the benefit of the conditions.

However, it is not widespread the combination of functional specifications with incremental execution phases, whereby the contract's object is definitively specified during its execution, allowing intermediate adjustments based on the results obtained at each stage (e.g., those found in engineering design methodologies with a design phase, an implementation phase, and a final evaluation phase).

The most notable example of this *modus operandi* is in pre-commercial public procurement procedures, not only with several phases but also with multiple awardees involved in a selective process.

In this regard, it is recommended to implement, in contracts that may profit of it, a set of phases that allows adjustments and revisions throughout the execution process, enabling greater flexibility and adaptation to changing needs.

2. Awarding procedures with dialogue

The awarding procedures with dialogue (competitive procedure with negotiation and competitive dialogue) are commonly utilized in Innovative Public Procurement (IPP) procedures. The regulation of these procedures outlines assumptions for applying the bidding procedure with negotiation, specifically indicating contract objects that involve a project or innovative solutions.

Indeed, it is usual to employ non-standard award procedures with dialogue to enhance flexibility, particularly during the tendering stage.

It is suggested to evaluate tender procedures different from the open procedure to better adapt to different contexts and needs, allowing a more specific and flexible approach in the selection of contractors and to adjust the proposals to the specific needs.

3. Award criteria based on value judgement and incentives for Goal Attainment

The use of award criteria subject to value judgement is quite widespread in the contract files analyzed, as well as avoiding the price criterion as the determining factor. This is logical as it facilitates the selection of offers that best fit the objectives and needs of the contract (taking into account criteria such as quality in design, execution planning, innovative content, etc.) apart from the price, increasing flexibility during the tender and the quality of the offer finally awarded.

In any case, for the sake of an appropriate application of criteria subject to value judgment, it is important that these criteria are formulated and applied objectively, with full respect for the principles of equality, non-discrimination, transparency and proportionality, and will not confer unlimited freedom of decision on the contracting authority. Anything that does not go this way may be subject to appeal by the bidders, with the consequent delays in the bid process.

We found some cases, in which the weight of the criteria based on value judgement exceeded that of the automatic ones. In these cases, the legislation requires the creation of a custom committee of experts to carry out the offer assessment, avoiding arbitrary reviews.

The assessment of value judgement criteria plays a crucial role in determining the flexibility of a contract. When the focus is primarily on “what” (i.e., the specific solution or product proposed by a supplier), the contract tends to be rigid and limits the ability to adapt to changes in the market, technological advancements. On the other hand, valuing the “how” (i.e. a supplier's approach, quality

processes, testing, and adaptability), provides greater flexibility during execution and fosters innovative solutions.

The recommendation is to focus on criteria that values processes and approaches, rather than concrete solutions. In this way, parties can more easily adapt to unexpected changes that take place throughout the performance of the contract.

The use of performance bonuses (incentives), although was only identified in PPI contracts, is by no means exclusive to it. In fact, it is recommended to apply it in those contracts in which the successful bidder must be "oriented" towards certain goals for the benefit of the contracting authority.

4. Admission of variants, options and contractual modifications

The inclusion of variants and the possibility of implementing foreseen modifications are common practices in the contracts analyzed. These measures provide the necessary flexibility to adapt to changes during the development of the contract, although the regulations for their definition and application are very restrictive in the national legislations.

In this sense, in our view, variants are considered to be of little practical use (especially if functional specifications are used) and difficult to implement in the tender procedure.

On the other hand, the modifications are considered really useful, although they require a clear identification of them when established.

The inclusion of options in some contracts gives the parties involved in the process the possibility to adapt to changes during the execution of the contract and allows them to introduce certain additional services or features, depending on their future needs.

It is essential to bear in mind that the bidding process involves the determination of a certain price. However, there exist the possibility of proposing modifications of the price during the contract lifetime, as long as it is reflected from the beginning in the estimated value of the contract.

The Preliminary Market Consultations are a very useful tool not only to establish tender specifications, but also to understand how the market perceives prices and to properly define the estimated value of contracts. This allows the contracting authority to adjust its expectations and requirements and align them with the reality of the market.

5. Intermediate milestones

Establishing flexible milestones may allow adapting the schedule to unforeseen circumstances or changes in the project without the need to modify the contract. It is important to take into account that changes in the date deadlines might be considered "substantial not planned modifications" and could be challenging to include.

Not setting specific deadlines and establishing them in post-award phases (i.e., Kick-off meeting) allow the parties to adjust the schedule without requiring modifications to the contract. Additionally, this facilitates aligning the schedule with the actual progress of the project, thus avoiding the application of penalties for delay.

An effective strategy to achieve greater flexibility in the deadlines for the execution of public contracts is to link the payment deadlines to specific deliverables rather than to specific dates, allowing adjustment of the deadlines according to the actual progress of the project and encouraging a more efficient execution of the contract.

6. Project Management Processes

Another tool identified suitable for promoting flexibility is the utilization of mechanisms facilitating seamless communication among the involved parties (project management processes). These mechanisms aim to identify potential risks, develop timely mitigation strategies, and enhance risk management.

Apart from the ones described above, although some other practices have been found to be beneficial to foster flexibility, they are in the minority or difficult to apply in the type of contracts considered in this study (e.g. progress clauses).

IV.3. References of the files analyzed in this study

Here below we list the files analyzed in this study. The full documents are available in the reference [9], as well as an analysis of the contracts of the different Laboratories.

<i>Institution</i>	<i>File Reference</i>	<i>Concept</i>
CIEMAT	282948	<i>Manufacture and supply of MCBXF series of nested dipole superconducting magnets.</i>
CIEMAT	291378	<i>Supply of prototype 400 kw peak solid-state radio frequency amplification system for the operation of radio frequency cavities of PARTICLE accelerators.</i>
CIEMAT	287625	<i>Detailed design, manufacture, supply, installation, commissioning and final testing of an experimental liquid lithium circuit and its auxiliary systems for lithium purification tests.</i>
CIEMAT	292848	<i>Manufacture, by laser sintering, and supply of MCBXF magnet coil spacers</i>
INFN	202000225MI	<i>Supply of Niobium RRR 300 and three related options for the creation of LB 650 cavities for the PIP-II project</i>
INFN	202100265MI	<i>Supply of two C-band RF plants with a maximum power of 42 MW and a repetition rate of 100 HZ</i>
INFN	202200432LNS_AMI	<i>Supply of a high-power laser with ultra-short pulses for the acceleration of charged particles and relative compressor chambers</i>

INFN	202100340MI	<i>Manufacture, testing, and delivery of two high-power C-band RF units, each of which includes a high-power solid-state modulator, a high-power C-band klystron, and an RF klystron.</i>
CEA	B23-05069	<i>Study and construction of a uniaxial press</i>
CEA	B23-02983-MDC	<i>Realization of the radio frequency quadrupole (RFQ) as part of the NEWGAIN PROJECT</i>
CEA	B23-04414-MR	<i>Acquisition of a robotic additive manufacturing cell using the WAAM (Wire Arc Additive Manufacturing) process for the robotics platform of the Grenoble plant.</i>
CEA	B23-00977-MBA	<i>Supply of nuclear measurement equipment (studies, dimensioning, production, on-site assembly, commissioning, testing, etc.) of nuclear measurement equipment for the construction of the VRAC-MI room at the Basic Nuclear Facility (BNI) No. 56 in CEA CADARACHE</i>
STFC	UKRI-2050	<i>Manufacture of large vacuum chambers.</i>
STFC	UKRI-1688	<i>EAI Lens Camera.</i>
STFC	UKRI-1892	<i>INTER vacuum vessel.</i>
STFC	DBB duct liners	<i>neutral beam duct liners</i>
ESS-Lund	V2020/1894	<i>Radio frequency cavities.</i>
ESS-Lund	V2023/557	<i>Sequencing systems.</i>
ESS-Lund	V2019/1944	<i>Optical Components for the MicroMAX Beamline</i>
ESS-Lund	V2021/2224	<i>Photon Counter Detector</i>
UPPSALA	UH2023/42	<i>X-ray diffractometer.</i>
UPPSALA	UH2023/29	<i>Refurbished high-resolution tandem mass spectrometer.</i>

Annex V: Glossary

Acronym	Definition
AIPF	Accelerator Industry Permanent Forum
AMICI	Accelerator and Magnet Infrastructure for Cooperation and Innovation. (Horizon 2020 Project GA No: 731086)
ASc&T	Accelerator Science and Technology
EC	European Commission
ILO	Industrial Liaison Office
IP	Intellectual Property
MS	Member State
RI	Research Infrastructure
TI	Technological Infrastructure
TIARA	Test Infrastructure and Accelerator Research Area Consortium
TRL	Technological Readiness Level
WP	Work-package